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Developments in political education in the austrian school system in the national, european, international and global context. Possible potentials through the use of digital media.

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I. INTRODUCTION

It is a fundamental aim of school education to enable pupils and young people to find their way around in the current society. In particular, to recognise and competently assess political, social and economic problem areas. Political communication and participation are essential prerequisites. Political education opens up very good opportunities here. In principle, this also includes an examination of the topics of democracy, freedom, justice, human rights, economic security and peace.

The research work in question, entitled "Political education in Austria historically and currently – Digital Media in Political Education" deals with political education in the Austrian school system. A good political education is necessary here, because areas of politics also affect our everyday life, this applies to political contents related to the nation state, but also to those in a European, international and global context. Pupils in Austria basically already have everyday experience with political problems, for which they would also like to see solutions from representatives of politics or politicians. Political instruction or (democratic) political education by committed, well-trained teachers in an optimum quality framework can contribute to the achievement of important competences, but can also have many more positive effects.

The historical retrospective of this research work begins with the fifth century BC and leads to the Xenophon's writing entitled "Cyropaedia", an ancient model for Fürstenspiegel ("Mirrors for princes"). A Fürstenspiegel is a document addressed to a ruler (e.g. prince, king) with exhortations for ethically unobjectionable conduct of office and with discussions of problems of state and social theory. Fürstenspiegel were topical until early modern times. During the epoch of modern times, national education, i.e. education for citizenship, became very important in European countries, including Austria. The path from civics to education for democratic politics took many decades and was marked by progress and regression.

This research work focuses on developments in political education in the Austrian school system since 1945, including the national state, European, national and global developments. In this context digital media are very important.

A substantial part is dedicated to the topic of digital media in political education. Contemporary young people obtain their information less via the so-called classical media, but increasingly use digital media. Digital media in the context of civic education open up

many (new) possibilities, but they also reveal limits. Information technologies are essential in many areas of life, including education. They are developing very dynamically, even with unforeseeable consequences for different areas of life. This also has a political, social and economic dimension. An analysis of studies on the topic of digital media in political education completes this research work, which is also reflected in a summary.

II. HISTORY FOR THE TEACHING OF POLITICS

1. BEGINNING OF POLITICAL EDUCATION

1.1. The first writings in the fifth century BC

According to the current state of research, the first writings on political education, here understood in the broadest sense, existed in Europe as early as the fifth century BC. An important example of this is "Cyropaedia", the "education of Cyrus", the Xenophon. "Cyropaedia" is a tendentious pedagogical novel, in which Xenophon tells the life story of Cyrus in poetic freedom and pragmatically develops its own thoughts about the upbringing and education of an ideal ruler. In these writings on political education the form of depicting an exemplary ruler was often chosen. The subjects of the time were thus also given the opportunity to criticise their current rulers. Xenophon also wrote other writings on state politics (Zeilner 2011, p 23).

Besides Xenophon, Aristotle from Stagira in Greece was of particular importance in ancient times for political writings, here also about the political education of the youth. In his "Politika" Aristotle was the advocate of a moderately democratic constitutional state based on a strong middle class. For him, politics was nothing other than applied ethics. From his point of view, the consideration of doing was only the preliminary stage and the theoretical part of ethics, but state theory is its applied and practical part. But Aristotle never completed his "doctrine of the ideal state". But Aristotle already spoke of the fact that...the legislator must above all take care of the education of the youth, nobody should doubt. Because if this does not happen in the states, it harms the constitutions, because the states must be administered in the same way as their respective constitutions (Zeilner 2011, p 23).

1.2. Fürstenspiegel for political education

In antiquity and later epochs, so-called "Mirrors for princes" were also essential for political education. Although political education was not yet a general topic in antiquity, political writings, in this case the "Fürstenspiegel", were known and used for the education of princes (Zeilner 2011, p 24 f).

In the history of political education and political thought, Fürstenspiegel is a literary genre in its own right. The addressees were princes, the authors also held the "Spiegel" (mirror) up to them. The political education of the prince and his way of governing were very important. In the context of pedagogy and political ethics and criticism of the ruler, they present and reflect the ideal image of a good prince. The concrete epoch is always essential here (Berges 1938, p 1 ff; cf. also Mühleisen/Stammen 1990).

The education of the princes of that time was either historically-biographically or theoretically-state-philosophically oriented. In their ideal demands, however, Fürstenspiegel were always subject to historical change. Among the most famous Fürstenspiegel, viewed in a historical longitudinal section, are Xenophon's "Cyropaedia", Seneca's writing "De Clementia", the eulogy of the younger Pliny to Emperor Trajan, the "Institutio Traiani" attributed to Plutarch in the Middle Ages and the "Formula vitae honestae" of Bishop Martin of Braga attributed to Seneca in the Middle Ages. In Greek-Byzantine literature, the late antique Ecthesis and the theological explanation of Deacon Agapetos for Justinian I are particularly noteworthy. Fürstenspiegel der Antike were also forerunners of the medieval Fürstenspiegel (Zeilner 2011, p 24 f).

Just as in ancient times, admonishing and instructive writings of the Middle Ages and early modern times were called Fürstenspiegel. They were usually addressed to a king, a prince (princeps) or their sons. The essential aim here was to set out the virtues and duties of a ruler and the principles of correct government. An important medieval prince's mirror is above all "Via regia", the first prince's mirror in Western Europe (around 812). In early modern times, for example, "Il Principe" (The Prince, 1513) by Niccolò Machiavelli and "Institutio Principes Christiani", the education of the Christian prince (1516), by Erasmus of Rotterdam, were significant (Zeilner 2011, p 26 f).

So there were mirrors of princes in different epochs, from antiquity and the Middle Ages to the Renaissance and early modern times. The Age of Enlightenment, however, also brought significant changes in the field of politics. Education for citizenship, or "national education", was already an educational programme of the French Enlightenment. With the Enlightenment and the processes of democratisation that followed it, political socialisation also became a fundamental problem of the political system. Within the framework of political socialisation, knowledge, values, norms, etc. are consciously and unconsciously imparted which orient, regulate and interpret political action (Zeilner 2011, p 29 f).

Looking back historically, the equality of all citizens and the (theoretically) only functional separation of the ruling and the ruled made a general political education necessary (Zeilner 2011, p 29 f).

2. NATIONAL EDUCATION, EDUCATION FOR CITIZENSHIP

2.1. National education (national pedagogy) as a process

In early modern Europe, the form of absolutist rule was constituted as a "federated state". The institution of school was essential for the implementation of goals, it had to fulfil state tasks. With the step towards a "civil society", educational goals were also modified. In the 17th and 18th centuries there were developments from the educational state via state education to national education or national education (Ulrich 1993, p. 1 ff).

National education is a process of consciously and/or unconsciously conveying "national cultural" values, norms, traditions etc. through state, such as schools, and/or social, such as family, (mass) media etc., socialisation bodies or institutions. The methodology and didactics of national education are time-bound and subject to change. However, it is always essential to focus on the subject of the nation or nation-state as a reference object and frame of reference for individual and collective education. In principle, the essential goal is to educate loyal and active citizens in the sense of an established national philosophy of state and society (Rittner 2012, S 1ff).

2.2. Joseph von Sonnenfels (1732-1817): Main aims of national education

During the modern era, national education, i.e. the education to become a (loyal) citizen, has also gained considerable importance in Austria. Joseph von Sonnenfels formulated the main objectives of this education system in a report: "Through scientific enlightenment the youth should receive the education necessary for their future destiny as citizens according to the diversity of classes. The education to become a citizen, however, presupposes the education to become a human being. The moralist educates the human being. Every citizen must have such moral principles which are in accordance with the laws of the State and prepare the State to observe them. This is the most splendid, but at the same time the most controversial praise of the sciences, that the attachment to the general order, the obedience to the laws increases, that they make the external coercion dispensable through inner conviction and make it possible to be less strict in punishment. The enlightened people will also always be the best subjects (Zeilner 2011, p 31).

Joseph von Sonnenfels, university lecturer and political scientist, was one of the team of advisors for Maria Theresa. In this report he addressed the ideological and educational task of the sciences in full clarity at the time. As an essential characteristic of Josephinism, it must never be overlooked in this context. The reform movement established at that time was already prepared during the 1760s to move further in the direction of the Enlightenment (Zeilner 2011, p 31).

2.3 The inauguration speech of Adolf Exner (1841-1894) in the 19th century: University of Vienna

For political education in the context of the Austrian education system, Adolf Exner's inauguration speech at the University of Vienna was of interest and directional. Exner, born in Prague in 1841, was a lawyer and professor of law, and he taught at several universities. In the academic year 1883/1884 he was Dean of the Faculty of Law and Political Science at the University of Vienna and was elected Rector of the University of Vienna for the academic year 1891/1892. In his inauguration speech, which was discussed controversially, Exner spoke out against an overestimation of scientific forms of thought and for the equivalence and independence of the humanities (Yearbook of the University of Vienna for the academic year 1893/1894; cf. also Österreichisches biographisches biographisches Lexikon 1815-1950).

In his inauguration speech, Exner also called for political education as a cross-disciplinary science for all faculties of the university. He saw the lack of civic education in the predominance of natural sciences that had shaped the entire 19th century and considered civic education for all students to be absolutely necessary because the 20th century "would be a political one". In his speech, he also specifically emphasised that skills – which he singled out as particularly characteristic – are inherent in every man of political education and only one. In his view, this also referred to the assessment of long gone times and their conditions. Only the politically educated man had the ability and the inclination to measure them according to their own measure. The uneducated, however, involuntarily brings the measure of the present to everything and thus underestimates past things and overestimates present things, which have always accompanied the political transformation (Zeilner 2011, p 34 f).

The great importance of civic education can be seen from this inauguration speech and from Exner's following sentences, among others: "Civic education thus includes the ability to do

justice to the past. But even more important than this, however, seems to me another side of the spirit honed by such education, which is turned towards the future. It has insight and a concept for "political necessities" and their counterpart "political impossibilities". According to Exner, this insight is particularly symptomatic (Zeilner 2011, p 35).

3. FROM CIVIC EDUCATION TO DEMOCRATIC POLITICAL EDUCATION, GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION AND OTHER (MODERN) DEVELOPMENTS

3.1 What can we learn from the history of political education in the Austrian school system?

It can be assumed that for political education related to the nation state, but above all through modern developments such as Global Citizenship Education, European Democratic Citizenship (EDC) etc., knowledge of historical developments in the subject is also necessary. Here, in particular, it is possible to identify developmental advances and regressions and their causes, as well as the intentions of legislators, etc. In everyday life the reference to politics is omnipresent, this concerns national, European and international politics. People are confronted with political content on a daily basis. These are for example topics of current politics, reports on crises and conflicts in different parts of the world, the globally discussed questions about culture and identities etc. Therefore, political education is fundamental and knowledge of the historical development of the subject is also essential. In order to understand the present, it is in any case also necessary to reflect on the history of crises. Understanding the historical and political science dimension of political, social, legal, economic, social and cultural developments is essential for (modern) political education (F.Zeilner 1991 - 2015).

3.2 Political education in Austria since the monarchy

Political education has been practised in Austria since the monarchy, initially under the name of "Bürgerkunde" (civics), which was a requirement that public education should provide basic knowledge of the nature of the state and society, and of the rights and duties of the individual towards both. Civic education was known in the philanthropic-rationalist pedagogy of the 18th and beginning of the 19th century in Germany ([www. zeno.org> Meyers-1905>Bürgerkunde, S 1](http://www.zeno.org/Meyers-1905/Bürgerkunde, S 1)).

In 1907, the Austrian education administration introduced a subject called "civics", the primary aim of which was to educate citizens who were loyal to the state. In 1907, civics lessons were introduced in the new curriculum for the third grade (= eighth grade) of the citizen schools within the framework of geography and history lessons. One year later, a separate subject was introduced at the high schools in Austria, but it was taught within the framework of geography and history lessons. Specifically, a new curriculum was adopted in 1908 in the course of a high school reform, in which a separate subject "civics" was provided for the eighth class with three lessons per week (Wolf 1998, p. 15).

In 1909, "civic education" was introduced by means of a curriculum in the "specialist further education schools", from which the vocational schools then developed. This inclusion of civics in the curriculum was also connected with the electoral law reform of 1907 demanded by Beck. "civic education". Turning towards the Austrian state, i.e. the promotion of patriotism, was an essential aim of civics education. After the collapse of the Austro-Hungarian monarchy in 1918 and the beginning of the republic, first the republic "German-Austria", then the "First Austrian Republic" with the federal constitution existing since 1920, there were now further interesting subjects for civics education (Zeilner 2011, p 40 f).

3.3. Political education in the interwar period

The term civics was followed by "civic education" or "civic education". The term "civics" was used primarily to teach institutional studies. This was basically the knowledge of the constitution, government, parliament, judiciary etc. This teaching was associated with a rather conflict-averse understanding of politics, oriented towards maintaining the existing political understanding (<https://austria-forum.org>>Politische Bildung/Politik/Essays im Austria Forum, p 1 ff).

Particularly significant changes with effects on the school system occurred in Austria, especially in the 1930s. With the resignation of the three presidents of the National Council, the end of democracy in Austria followed. As early as 1933, schools also became part of the authoritarian politics that already existed at that time. School, especially political education at school, soon became the focus of these interests. The institution school was instrumentalised to legitimise the new power relations. This also meant that the school system was now used directly and openly as an instrument of government policy. In May 1933 it was decreed that "patriotic education" should be given special emphasis as an educational content. The

curricula following this decree and the selected textbooks now had the premises of "religious-moral", "patriotic-Austrian" and "social-ethnic" as contents of political education (Zeilner 2011, p 52 f).

3.4 Political education during Austrofascism and the Nazi regime and the Second World War

Austrofascism:

In 1934, the curriculum content was adapted to the goals of Austrofascism (Ständestaat). At that time – after a significant change in the content of the textbooks – the new textbooks also contained so-called "ideals" or "values" in the context of this authoritarian regime. For example "heroism", "resistance", "willingness to make sacrifices" etc. These contents should be taught to pupils in the sense of a political education. It was also an essential aim of the school to educate pupils in all subjects to classify them without conflict and to comply with prescribed duties and norms. The rulers of Austrofascism at that time had the right to determine by which means and for whose benefit politics was conducted, and the school system also served this purpose (Zeilner 2011, p 54).

Nazi regime:

The annexation of Austria to the German Reich in 1938 also brought about major changes in the school system. The pupils or the entire youth were to be made available for the policies of the Nazi regime. Citizenship education was not available as a separate subject, because political education in the sense of this regime had to be provided in every subject. "Political education" in the sense of the Nazi regime was not only the content of the subjects taught, but also the way in which they were taught and how the "rules" of school coexistence were basically shaped. The so-called "Gleichschaltungskurs" (no different opinions allowed) was carried out very quickly and uncompromisingly. This "political education", especially in extra-curricular institutions, continued until the end of the Second World War or the Nazi regime. After 1945, the development of political education in Austria was different from that in Germany, where the subject of "re-education" was very important. This was the democratic educational work planned and carried out by the Allies in connection with denazification throughout post-war Germany (Zeilner 2011, p 36 f).

4. POLITICAL EDUCATION FROM 1945 TO THE END OF THE 20TH CENTURY

4.1. The roots of traditional civic education

Traditional political education has its roots in political science, history and education. The aim was and is to recognise connections in political events, to convey and strengthen tolerance and the ability to accept criticism, and thus to contribute above all to the formation and further development of active citizenship and to social and political participation (Zeilner 2011).

4.2. Different developments in Germany and Austria:

After the Second World War, a re-education or democracy programme was started in Germany at the instigation of the "Allies". This necessity was not seen as necessary for Austria at that time, which, however, caused a certain backlog in political education (Zeilner 2011).

There were two main reasons for this situation at Austrian schools after the Second World War. The first was the fear of ideological national education and the second was the fact that Austria's role in the war and in the National Socialist system should have been addressed. This would also not have been in conformity with the "victim thesis" officially advocated at that time (<https://www.pfz.at/themen-entwicklungspolitik/harmonie-als-demokratisches-prinzip-politische-bildung-in-oesterreich-nach-1945>, p. 1).

After the Second World War, the new curricula in Austria were based on those of the interwar period, which, among other things, aimed at promoting a sense of homeland awareness, where subordination to the state and the general public was essential. This "civic education" promoted neither the ability to criticise nor the formation of pupils' own opinions and differs considerably from the modern political education and understanding of the present, such as on the subject of democracy (Zeilner 2011).

Towards the end of the 1950s, democracy in areas of Austrian politics and political education meant finding a consensus in principle. The individual had to subordinate himself to the state and the general public. This also meant a balance between individual freedom and established framework conditions.

Citizenship education" as a school subject should make a significant contribution here (https://www.pfz.at/themen-development_policy/harmony_as_a_democratic_principle-political_education_in_Austria_after_1945, p. 1).

4.3. The introduction of social studies in combination with the subject history

In the 1960s, social studies were introduced in combination with history. This combination of subjects emerged in the lower and upper secondary levels from 1962 onwards in the course of the reorganisation of the Austrian school system in the so-called School Organisation Act (SCHOG 62).

At that time, the introduction of social studies in combination with the subject history and the AHS curriculum for the upper school for the subject history and social studies was an important development for civic education (Academic Senate, Yearbook of the University of Salzburg 1975-1977, p 13).

This AHS-curriculum contained the following at that time:

"The thorough treatment of the history of Austria and civic education should lead to respect for the achievements of the past and open-mindedness for the tasks of the present and the future and strengthen civic awareness. The social studies curricula should enable a better understanding of historical processes as well as social orders and their development, lead to a higher sense of social responsibility, encourage active participation in public life and contribute to a lifestyle characterised by tolerance and humanity" (AHS-curriculum history and social studies, upper school).

There were also concerns at the time about the introduced combination of history and social studies. Among other things, the opinion was expressed that the subject of history was already much overloaded and that the working methods were very different from those of social studies. History shows how the world has developed, but civic education has to theorise the historical material on the basis of systematic criteria or according to the respective functionality of political institutions (Akademischer Senat, Jahrbuch der Universität Salzburg 1975-1977, p. 13).

4.4. The beginning of education for democracy

In this context, steps have now been initiated and implemented in Austria which have opened up a new field of vision, namely that of civic education. The decree on civic education, which had been in force since 1949, was now gradually becoming too narrow to

be able to meet the general demand for the "responsible citizen". Civic education only fulfilled part of what pupils needed to find their way around the political world (Rada 1980, p 10).

Until the 1960s, the aim of political education in Austrian schools was an education towards the state. This education of pupils began as early as 1869, when the institution of school was removed from the sphere of influence of the church. From the second half of the 1960s onwards, a slow start was made to promote "education for democracy" to the centre of political education. However, the educational guidelines for the Austrian school system laid down in this connection became increasingly inefficient at that time (Wolf 1998, p. 9).

In the 1960s, in the context of the so-called "68 Movement", new approaches to political education also started to be promoted. The effects were then also visible in schools. In 1974, the subject "political education" was to be established in the final classes of AHS and BHS. This failed at the time due to multiple resistance, but in 1978 it led to the fundamental decree of political education as a teaching principle. This decree did not, however, lead to political education becoming an essential part of teacher training. However, they were expected to take political education into account or to address it in their teaching subjects (<https://www.pfz.at/themen-entwicklungspolitik/harmo-nie-als-democratic-principle-political-education-in-Austria-after-1945>, p. 1).

4.5. The introduction of the working group "History and Social Studies – Geography and Economics"

Decision-makers in the Austrian school system believed at the time that a modern civics education would develop from the interaction of social studies and economics, which is why the introduction of the working group "History and Social Studies – Geography and Economics" for the eighth classes of the AHS was a further important step in the 1971/72 school year. In order to develop this contemporary civics, the non-binding exercise "Political Education", which had been introduced for the eighth class of the AHS in the 1972/73 school year, was extended to the seventh class (Folkmann 1988, p. 14).

In addition to significant work for the establishment of the basic decree, a further step was taken in 1976 in the AHS sector to promote political education in the classroom (Academic Senate, University of Salzburg Yearbook 1975-1977, p. 15).

4.6. The extension of the non-binding exercise "Political Education"

The non-binding exercise Political Education, which was introduced for the eighth grade of the AHS in the 1971/72 school year, was extended to the sixth grade from the 1976/77 school year. The aim of this non-binding exercise was set out in the specific curriculum as follows: "In a working group on "civic education", the pupil should acquire knowledge of factors and functional relationships of the orders and events in politics, the economy and society. The young person is to gain criteria for arriving at critical judgement and rationally controlled decisions. Initiative and self-activity on the part of the pupil are essential prerequisites for this (Academic Senate, University of Salzburg Yearbook 1975-1977, p. 15).

4.7. The 1978 Decree of Principles: legal bases, recommendations and guidelines for the teaching principle

§ 2 School Organisation Act:

§ 2 of the School Organisation Act (SchOG) of 1962 was and is an essential legal basis for the teaching principle of civic education. Specifically, these are the tasks of the Austrian school mentioned therein (§ 2 SchOG). In addition, there are also international recommendations and guidelines which emphasise the high priority of Civic Education and the right of young people to it. Civic education was established in 1978 as a teaching principle for all school forms, school levels and subjects (school subjects). This comprehensive mandate and the objectives of civic education in the school sector have been and continue to be a central element in fulfilling the tasks set out in § 2 of the School Organisation Act. Political education was and is seen as a prerequisite for individual development and also for the further development of the social whole. It is also an active contribution to shaping society and to anchoring or consolidating democracy. Political education also leads to essential questions, for example "how rule and authority are recognised by society as legitimate". It is committed to the democratic understanding that the free appointment, control and retrievability of the rulers by the ruled, rule and authority in a democracy legitimises (https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/Themen/schule/schulrecht/rs/1997-2017/2015_12.html, S 1 f).

Political education as the central foundation of a democratic society:

In this basic decree, political education was clearly defined as the central foundation of a democratic society and as the task of the Austrian school. The implementation of this first teaching principle in practice, however, took place very differently and depends on the commitment and level of teachers (Mittnik et al 2018, p 18 f).

A contemporary political education:

As early as in the 1978/79 school year, the basic decree "Political Education in Schools" in Austria put into practice the longstanding efforts to introduce a modern political education in schools. At that time, contemporary civic education was understood to mean a civic education that takes account of the pluralistic, conflictual character of democratic societies. The aim is to encourage pupils to take their own standpoints and to learn to critically question the existing situation. In essence, this decree represents a clear departure from the "civic education" of 1949 which had been in force until then, as is also evident from the understanding of politics formulated in the basic decree (Wolf 1998, p. 8).

The political understanding on which the decree is based can be clearly seen from the wording of its content (basic decree "Political education in schools"):

"Essential concerns of political education are the education of a democratically founded awareness of Austria, of pan-European thinking and of a cosmopolitanism based on an understanding of people's existential problems. Civic education is committed to an understanding of democracy which, in the recognition of legitimate rule and authority, does not contradict the postulated identity of governments and the governed. At the centre, however, is the question of how rule and authority are recognised as legitimate by society: in a democratic community, the unalterable characteristic will be that authority and rule are drawn from the source of free ordering, free control and free recall by the governed or by the organs appointed by them. A democratic system of government will be all the more successful the more the idea of democracy is recognised in other areas of society" (Baumgartner 2007, p 12).

If one looks at the content and the entirety of the decree on "civic education in schools" against the background of the historical development in Austria up to this point in time, it can be stated as a major result that there has been a break with tradition. This is certainly most clearly expressed by the fact that the term "state" does not appear once in the entire

decree and has now been replaced by the term "democracy", which is so essential for civic education.

The basic decree on the teaching principle of civic education from 1978 specified concrete concerns and also named three areas as the basis for teaching civic education:

- Political education is the imparting of knowledge and skills: Pupils should gain insight into the orders and various forms of political, cultural and economic life.
- Political education is the development of skills of insight: Political, cultural and economic connections are to be recognised and critical judgement acquired.
- Political education is the awakening of a willingness to act responsibly: pupils should be prepared to help shape political processes on their own initiative (BMUKK 2006, p. 7).

It is very important how the conviction is awakened in pupils that democracy is not limited to an inwardly uninvolved adherence to its rules, but that it also requires a high degree of commitment and education. To stand up for inviolable basic values such as human dignity, human rights, above all freedom, etc., was laid down in the 1978 decree of principles in the basic guidelines for the organisation of teaching. For example also through the following concrete proposals for teaching: these are promotion of the experience of democratic attitudes and behaviour, starting the learning processes from the pupils' area of experience, open presentation and discussion of different views in dialogue, cooperation between school and parents (BMUKK 2006, p. 7).

Objectives of an interdisciplinary education Political education is the recognition of social structures and interrelationships; the awakening of the conviction that democracy requires a high degree of commitment and the willingness to participate personally in the democratic decision-making process; the development of a tolerant attitude towards political dissidents; the understanding of the tasks of comprehensive national defence; the promotion of the readiness to stand up for inviolable basic values such as freedom and human dignity (re-decree of the basic decree of 1978).

This basic decree lays down the principles, objectives and implementation of political education in Austrian schools. In addition to national (Austrian) standards, this decree also refers to the Council of Europe Charter on Political Education and Human Rights Education (Basic Decree on Political Education).

4.8. The decree of the BMU to add the term "political education" to the compulsory optional subject "history and social studies" in 1989

The year 1989 was particularly important for the AHS sector. A decree of the BMU added the term "political education" to the compulsory optional subject "history and social studies" in the upper secondary schools of the AHS. In 1991, the term "civics" was gradually replaced by "political education" in the BMS and BHS in those subjects which included the word "civics" (Wolf 1998, p. 8).

The term "political education" was now available in the Austrian school system. However, a definition of this term in terms of content was and is very difficult; this can be based, for example, on the function of political education or its form. In areas of politics, science, etc., this term is in any case discussed controversially (Ackermann 1999, p 185).

In analogy to Germany, political education should in any case be understood as the teaching of the principles of democracy, tolerance and the ability to criticise as well as the ability to actively participate in political events. It should be clear to all attempts to define "civic education" that it is one of the key qualifications on the way to becoming a responsible citizen. Only those who are politically educated can help shape political events, this concerns the nation state, European and international politics (www.bildungsexperten.net, p. 1 ff).

4.9. The basic decree on the teaching principle of civic education: re-launched in 1994:

In 1994, the decree on political education GZ 33.464/6-19a/78 was reissued under the reference number GZ 33.466/103-V/4a/94. Political education was seen as a prerequisite both for the personal development of individuals and for the further development of society, and thus as a contribution to the realisation of democracy. At that time, the education of a democratically founded awareness of Austria, of pan-European thinking and of a cosmopolitan attitude based on an understanding of the existential problems of humanity were essential concerns of political education (BMUKK and Zentrum Polis, p. 7).

4.10. Political education towards the end of the 20th century

Links to other subjects: Interdisciplinary links:

Towards the end of the 20th century, the links between political education and other subjects also became increasingly evident in Austria. Hardly any other subject or subject canon in the school sector had as many interdisciplinary points of contact as political education (Klepp/Rippitsch (eds.) 2008, p. 233).

These points of contact also led to important steps in development. It can be assumed that the "framing" of a subject is very important for the systematic acquisition of knowledge, but at the same time the limits of the questions included in the subject become visible here. Interdisciplinary and cross-curricular political education is not only an important complement to the teaching of the subject, but should also contribute to its completion. This assumption or position, taken from the 1997 BLK report on possible consequences of TIMSS for mathematics and science teaching, contains a programme for a far-reaching change in teaching in general education schools in Germany. It can also be applied to other subjects. Teaching in the subject and teaching that combines subjects will also increasingly be linked in organisational terms. Above all, the links to other knowledge models are essential; here, for example, learning outcomes from subject teaching can be applied well. This can or should lead to new tasks and questions. School learning outcomes will become up-to-date and can be linked to new content. For example, the Council of Europe programme or European political education (BLK Gutachten 1997).

The Council of Europe programme:

The programme of the Council of Europe called "Education for Democratic Citizenship" (EDC), which was and is particularly important for political education, was and is intended to provide a basis for stronger measures for political education throughout Europe in terms of content and arguments. The objectives postulated for the school sector in particular provided directions for defining decisive aspects of learning, further developing teaching and participation structures and making progress in the difficult area of evaluation. (Diendorfer/Steininger 2006, p 233 f).

In the 21st century, European political education or the topic of Europe is already an integral part of Austrian curricula. Looking back historically, the so-called "Objective Paragraph", which defines the tasks of Austrian schools, stipulated that young Austrians should be

enabled to participate in the economic and cultural life of Europe (School Organisation Act, Objective Paragraph: § 2).

Looking back at the 20th century, it can be said that significant steps have been taken in the development of political education. However, there were also periods with little progress. In Hellmuth's view, this was particularly true of the late 1980s and the 1990s. At the beginning of the 21st century, further significant developmental steps were taken, such as the lowering of the active voting age from 18 to 16 years and the associated changes in the teaching of politics, the democracy initiative "Entscheidend bist du" ("You decide"), etc. The interest in political education has fundamentally increased and there has also been an intensive didactic discussion. Theory models and methods of teaching politics were also focused on and a competence structure model was developed (<https://www.pfz.at/themen-entwicklungspolitik/harmonie-als-demokratisches-prinzip-politische-bildung-in-oesterreich-nach-1945>, p. 1).

Political education is (still) integrated in other subjects:

In any case, one major shortcoming is that until the end of the 20th century and even up to now, the Austrian school system did not and still does not have a separate subject "political education" as a separate subject. Political education is integrated into other subjects, such as "History and Political Education", "Political Education and Law", etc. Universities and colleges of education also do not yet have their own subject "Political Education" for student teachers. The compulsory combination of study courses is called "History, Social Studies and Political Education", as is also the case for one subject. If one considers the developmental steps of political education in the Austrian school system, these have been from civics, to civic education or civic studies, to political education, to democratic political education including modern developments such as "global citizenship education", EDC etc. that are relevant to teaching (Zeilner 2011, p 1 ff).

A particularly important step in the 20th century was, among other things, the basic decree of 1978 issued by Fred Sinowatz, then Minister of Education in Bruno Kreisky's government (Basic Decree on Political Education 1978).

Since then, political education has been a teaching principle at Austrian schools. The aim here is not only to impart knowledge about the state and society in an interdisciplinary manner but also to awaken or promote the willingness to engage in politics and to act in a factually sound and responsible manner (GZ 33.466/103-V/4a/94).

In the overall context of developments in civic education in Austria up to the end of the 20th century, developments in other (Western) countries should also be examined. In Germany, for example, in 1997 the Federal Agency for Civic Education and the regional agencies for civic education formulated the tasks of civic education in the 21st century in the so-called "Munich Manifesto". One of the demands of the Munich Manifesto, entitled "Democracy needs political education", is that political education in the public domain should be pluralistic, non-partisan and independent (Munich Manifesto 1997).

4.11. Developments in policy lessons in the Austrian school system in the 21st century

Compulsory subject "History and Political Education" in AHS from 2001: media competence was already essential

In 2001, the discipline "political education" was included in the AHS compulsory subject "History and Political Education", which was particularly important for the sustainable development of the subject in the school sector. With a unanimous decision of the National Council and the four parliamentary parties of the time, i.e. the ÖVP, SPÖ, FPÖ and the Greens, the new subject title "History and Political Education" was introduced for the seventh and eighth grades of the AHS. This meant that the AHS made up for what had already been achieved in other upper school forms in previous years by a parliamentary two-thirds majority by replacing the word "civics" with the much broader term "political education" in the relevant compulsory subjects (Austrian Education News 2002, p. 1 ff).

This establishment as a compulsory subject was also an important step for this subject, because there was already a reduction of lessons in the upper school. The new curriculum adopted in 2002 placed particular demands on the teachers to teach everyday political understanding, actors in international and national politics and the role of the (mass) media. As with the previous curriculum, methodological competence was of particularly high relevance. The term "media democracy" already existed at that time (Molnar 2008, p. 239).

The Council of Europe Declaration: entitled "Democracy Education" (2005)

Austria's commitment to the Council of Europe was and is of great importance to it. This concerns above all the areas of human rights, culture and education and social affairs (children's rights, women's rights, non-violence). These are also important contents for political education, especially for democracy education (<https://www.bmbwf.gv.at>, p. 1 ff).

In this context, 2005 was a very important year for civic education, both at school and outside school, because the European Council declared or recommended that "civic education" should in future be called "education for democracy". From this point on, one should actually speak of "education for democratic politics". The addition of "democracy" before "political education" was an essential premise at that time and the year 2005 was also declared the Year of Democracy Education. The main aim was to interest more citizens in politics and also to encourage them to become politically active, but especially to educate pupils in this direction (Diendorfer/Steininger 2006, p 95 ff).

The Council of Europe is active in the field of (democratic political) education with many initiatives. A major example is the "Charter for Political Education and Human Rights Education" adopted by 47 member states in 2010. It is an essential reference for the work of the Council of Europe and other organisations at European and international level. The Charter reaffirms that civic and human rights education should enable people to play an active role in a democratic society. Democracy education requires skills that enable people to take an active role and responsibility in society. A reference framework for democratic competences has been developed for this purpose. This basic model comprises twenty competences, including about two thousand descriptors, and is divided into three competence levels (basic, intermediate, advanced) (<https://www.bmbwf.gv.at>, S 1 ff).

Start of the development of the Austrian competence structure model for political education (2007):

In 2007 the development of the Austrian competence structure model for civic education with four areas of competence began. Through political education, pupils are to be given subject-specific competences, i.e. subject competence, methodological competence, judgement competence and action competence in key policy areas. For this reason, a commission appointed by the BMUKK also worked out a so-called "Competence structure model for political education" from December 2007 to March 2008. This model was intended to define and describe in more detail the competences to be acquired through Civic Education which mature Austrian citizens with voting rights acquire during their socialisation for socio-political and democratic reasons (Krammer 2008, p 5 f).

By acquiring these competences, pupils should have a repertoire of approaches and key political competences, such as democracy, law, gender, etc., which can be applied in different situations. On the basis of these competences, the interest in political events and

the willingness to actively participate in them should be promoted. Concrete experiences of the pupils are very important here. Competence-oriented political education enables pupils to form their own opinion and to be able to articulate it. It also encourages self-reflection and respect and recognition of controversial views. It is very important that pupils acquire a critical judgement of the (political) opinion of others and of the presentation of contents in the media. In this context, media competence is especially important (https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/Themen/schule/schul-recht/rs/1997-2017/2015_12.html, p 3).

In Austria, so-called working knowledge was already the basis for the acquisition of competences in the field of political education. This is event related, has an instrumental character and only enables political learning processes that were or are necessary for the development of political competences. In any case, this includes a reflected and (self-)reflexive political awareness of the pupils and ideally also has points of contact with their everyday life (Praxis Politische Bildung 2009,p 11).

Political education in the subject "history and political education" on the timetable of all eighth grade schools (2008/2009):

From the 2008/2009 school year onwards, political education was then also a fixed item on the timetable of all eighth grades in the subject "History and Political Education". From then on, this subject was now enshrined in law and the legally relevant curriculum was redesigned. The Minister responsible at the time, Dr Claudia Schmied, explained in this respect that with the reduction of the active voting age to 16 years, it became necessary to intensify civic education in Austria's schools (OÖ. Nachrichten, 15.05.2008., p. 4).

At the same time, the Austrian Federal Government launched a "democracy offensive" which led to the lowering of the voting age to the age of 16. The curriculum of lower secondary school was redesigned for the subject History and Social Studies/Political Education (GSKPB). In this curriculum, political competences were made compulsory for the first time (Mittnik 2018, p 18 f).

Revision of the basic decree "Political education in schools" (2015) and a new curriculum for history and social studies/political education (2016):

In 2015, the basic decree "Political Education in Schools" (first published in 1978) was revised by the then Federal Ministry of Education and Women. This decree describes the contents and implementation of the teaching principle. It is also intended as a guideline for initial, further and continuing education and represents a recommendation for other measures in the field of civic education. The basic decree from 1978 has been updated with this revision in the sense of a contemporary political didactics. All teachers, school supervisors and other school administrators are thus called upon to support the effective implementation of civic education by forwarding this basic document and with suitable accompanying measures (https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/Themen/schule/schulrecht/rs/1997-2017/2015_12.html, p. 1).

On 18 May 2016, the Federal Law Gazette. II No. 113/2016 a new curriculum for history and social studies/political education (GSK/PB) was announced. This was an important step in the implementation of the government programme to strengthen political education from the 6th school year onwards. This new curriculum then came into force in ascending order with the 2016/2017 school year. In parallel, the previous curriculum was phased out (BGBl. II No. 113/2016).

The main features of this curriculum comprise a total of nine thematic modules per school level, of which two modules are political education, two modules are historical-political learning and five modules are historical learning. Recurring basic concepts such as domination, power relations, gender, participation, scope for action, etc., which are relevant both in the historical field and in current politics, promote networked learning. Age-appropriate curriculum content and elements for testing political action. Questions that enable the examination of both longitudinal historical sections and cross-sectional comparisons are essential in this context (BGBl. II No. 113/2016).

The bundling of topics into modules, as provided for in this curriculum, made it possible to focus on the orientation of students in time and space, the critical search for identity in a pluralistically constituted society, and the development of independent historical and political thought and action. Controversial interests in dealing with history and politics can be recognised as such by the pupils. In the sense of a democratically constituted society, they are enabled to articulate their own opinions, to accept those of others, but also to reflect and critically question them. The aim of the course is to develop in the pupils a reflected and (self-)reflected awareness of history and politics as well as their own repertoire of actions (BGBl. II No. 113/2016).

Of the total of nine thematic modules, two each were or are intended for political education and historical-political learning and five modules for historical learning. The introduction of the compulsory modules was already announced for autumn 2015, but the start was then postponed for a pilot project at 53 schools. At that time, the experiences of teachers also flowed into this curriculum. For the Ministry of Education this curriculum was a "milestone in the teaching of political education and democratic culture (<https://www.wienerzeitung.at>, p 1 ff).

Pilot project 2017/2018 and curriculum for compulsory practice and "digital literacy" (2018/2019):

In the 2017/2018 school year, the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education" was launched as a pilot project at 178 new secondary schools and lower secondary schools. Starting in the 2018/ 2019 school year, a prescribed curriculum for the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education" was then implemented at new secondary schools and AHS lower grades ([https:// lehrer-web. wien> single>news,](https://lehrer-web.wien>single>news) Schule 4.0: Neue Medien und Lerntechnologien in Theorie und Praxis, S 1 ff).

Within four years, pupils should acquire skills in the areas of the following areas within the scope of two to four hours per week Social aspects of media change and digitalisation, information, data and media competence, operating systems and standard applications, media design, digital communication and social media, security, technical problem solving and computational thinking. Schools can decide for themselves whether they teach the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education" in special lessons or integrated into other subjects (Ordinance of the Federal Minister of Education, Science and Research amending the Ordinance on the Curricula of New Secondary Schools and the Ordinance on the Curricula of General Secondary Schools; BGBl. II No.71/2018).

For example, schu-le.at, in cooperation with Playmit, produced twenty-six (26) short videos on the subsections of the curriculum for "Digital Basic Education". A commentary or explanation in the short sequences of which contents can be assigned to the individual areas is available here (schule.at, MY DIGITALES SCHULPORTAL).

The teaching material for this compulsory exercise is divided into eight thematic areas. The Vienna Education Server deals well with possible problems in this context. This means that if a school decides to offer "digital basic education" as a separate teaching subject, strategic considerations are necessary. Many contents cannot be dealt with in a double lesson, there is also the risk of a reduction in content. Digital basic education is not a computer science lesson, so teachers of all subjects should be able to teach it. In the case of integrative implementation, a committed and interdisciplinary well co-operating team, including an optimal quality framework, is essential, especially regarding technical resources. The ability to work in a team and good teacher training are very important here (Lehrerweb.wien, Digital Basic Education).

5. THE RECORDING OF HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENTS IN THE DIGITAL CONTEXT: THE ISSUE OF "DIGITALITY" IN EDUCATION

5.1. Media as a central component of teaching

Over the centuries, not only has the intensity of use of many media changed, but the range of "teaching media" used has also expanded considerably. At first, books were important for the school sector, at certain points and then widely used. This was followed by the development of a further standard for teaching media in schools, both acoustic and visual. In the early 1980s, the computer established itself as a central media innovation and as a measurement medium. Digital media were already part of the standard, but their presence does not yet enable them to be used effectively and meaningfully. Adaptation efforts by teachers and pupils are necessary (www.lmz-bw.de, p 1 ff).

The use of media in the context of teaching and learning or in the classroom requires above all media education (media literacy) and also interest in technologies. In this case, these are information technologies. Instructional media have been anchored in the educational context or in school lessons for a long time. They have now been expanded to include digital media, the development and evolution of which is proceeding very rapidly. For a long time, the role of teachers was primarily that of imparting knowledge; contemporary pupils are now more intensively involved in the development of educational content. Digital media in particular have great potential here. Research into "digitality" and its developments is very important and topical for the education sector (www.lmz-bw.de, p 1 ff).

5.2. Exploring "digitality" in schools: developments at three levels

In the context of heterogeneous interactions at the intersection of language and society with a focus on school education (political education) and the topic of "digitality", developments can be recorded on three levels:

Firstly, in some cases, discourses are changing in school educational media, especially new and sometimes also different educational contents are being offered by actors who have not produced or are not producing textbooks, but who are currently developing digital (teaching) materials of basically good didactic, technical and aesthetic quality.

Secondly, education is changed by the way digital educational media are used. The way they are used prioritises certain discourses and practices. For example, individual competition is presented as desirable when the focus is on winning. In contrast, collective knowledge generation is preferred when cooperative writing tools are used. This is nothing new in principle and also in the field of education.

Thirdly, discourses on digitality form the framework for how and by whom education is structured and shaped in the digitally networked world of today (Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung. Digital educational media in discourse. Value systems, effectiveness and alternative concepts).

Developments in the field of "digitality" are fundamental for the education sector, here of course also for political education. In this context, developments in civic education do not only have an impact on the national state, but especially on international, European and global ones. For the field of research this means an examination of the past, the present and the future in the context of these developments, especially with information and communication technologies.

5.3. Example: Political education 2.0

Digitisation and new information and communication technologies have brought about and continue to bring about changes in society, particularly in the education sector and at school. The amount of information, collaboration, participation and networking through digital networks characterise communication in the context of the everyday life of pupils, children and young people. As didactic principles, they must find their way into the educational system and into concrete educational areas. From the point of view of communication science, possible perspectives are to be discussed and illustrated by means of project

examples. For example, the project example "PoliPedia.at" is currently very topical (Atteneder/Maier-Rabler 2016, p 1 ff).

Political education in the context of Civic Education 2.0 and in other areas of "digitality" also leads to a media competence-oriented professional requirement profile. This includes adaptation achievements of teachers and pupils. Pedagogues and specialists trained in media education have meanwhile become important for the educational sector and working life, which also includes the ability of all actors to work in a team. In practice, media education in the context of political education is often based on this requirement profile. In political education the core competences for media pedagogical action are media competence and media pedagogical competence. A professionalisation of political education in the field of media pedagogy also requires consideration in the training of pedagogues and political educators in the context of teacher training at universities and colleges of education. Here the subject of (political) communication and media is particularly important. This also means political communication (Hugger 2017, p 182 f).

In the age of the data explosion, the media are the key authority in political education and media competence is the goal of political education, as has already been shown. The question also arises here, what does media competence do for the quality of democracy and the understanding of democracy and politics? First of all, it must be said that we are living in an age of information explosion. The digital data explosion changed the world and our lives in a radical way. As of the beginning of 2013, 3.7 million e-mails were sent worldwide per second and within three months about 18 billion photos were uploaded to Facebook. 90 % of the existing data worldwide originates from the last two years. The topic of "Big Data"¹ is also relevant for the field of political education and democratic political education (www.academia-superior.at).

This "datafication" is revolutionary but also involves great risks, because it also provides new insights into very many areas of our lives. This also applies to the so-called "privacy". Everything that is and will be also has a date, this concerns the past, the present and the future. Even things and events that have hardly been noticed up to now will be datafused.

¹ In this respect, it is also important for students to know that our behaviour is becoming more predictable from day to day as the amount of data we leave behind increases. The computing power of computers is also constantly being improved in order to capture these huge amounts of data and also to create new cross-connections between these data or to link them. This has also become necessary in the field of mass media (Die Presse, Friday, 10 May 2013, p 1).

These data are also very well usable. It is essential to make pupils aware of this in politics lessons, because in many cases this also involves the protection of privacy, (economic) crime, etc. The publication effect of mass media is enormously high and also associated with risks. Above all, the networking of data is also very problematic. The importance of the media is, however, controversially discussed, and there is often a mistrust of the media even among pupils (Die Presse, Friday, 10 May 2013, p. 1).

It should also be pointed out here that other developments besides the topic of "digitality" are also important for political education or political communication. This is, for example, the importance of "algorithms" in people's lives, which is increasing. Especially also the influence of algorithms on social and political communication and decision making. Essential questions here are, for example, "How exactly do algorithms influence our social coexistence and what are the challenges for democracy and education? (www.bpb.de/learning/media/pedagogy). "The influence of algorithms on social and political communication and decision-making", p. 1).

This probably includes many challenges in the context of algorithms. Modern research is already focusing and investigating the influence of algorithms on social and political communication and decision making* (lindemedia.at/news-bfgjournal, S 1ff).

5. CONSEQUENCES FOR THE EDUCATION SYSTEM THROUGH COVID-19 (BEGINNING 2020)

The corona pandemic accelerates change:

The corona pandemic led to great uncertainty, which also affected the educational sector and the world of work. In the educational sector, the situation led above all to "distance learning", in the world of work to "home office". In both areas, previously familiar patterns had to be broken up. In times of lockdowns "distance learning" and "home office" have become buzzwords (F. Zeilner)

The assessment of the situation by UNICEF:

Covid-19 already caused a worldwide education crisis in spring 2020. For example, about one in three children had no access to digital media or distance learning. UNICEF assessed this situation very critically and came to the conclusion that one third of the pupils (more than 460 million) worldwide had no access to distance learning for many weeks during the

school closures caused by COVID-19. According to UNICEF, this situation points to a global education crisis. The economic impact is likely to last for some time (Forte Henrietta, UNICEF Executive Director).

At the time of the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic or the local and national lockdown, around 1.5 billion pupils were unable to attend school. Relevant data in this respect were taken from the "Remote Learning Reachability Report".

According to UNICEF, however, the situation could be even worse in reality, because not everything is or can be covered in this report. Many pupils do not have the necessary technology or digital media at their disposal, but in addition, pupils who do for other reasons, such as compulsory work, lack of or no assistance in using online services, etc. could not learn from a distance. This clearly includes educational and developmental disadvantages, especially for younger people in important stages of development. UNICEF points out that education systems, including schools, need to be strengthened to cope with such crises as well as possible. The application of "Distance Learning" is essential for all pupils, but disadvantaged children need special support (Forte Henrietta, UNICEF Executive Director).

In this context, pupils should also be made aware of the importance of the United Nations (UN), above all of its children's relief organisation UNICEF, a development policy organisation. Political education is very suitable for this purpose. For pupils, knowledge of the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic and of the measures to contain it is essential. The negative consequences are manifold and pose great challenges for societies worldwide. Essential information on political, social and economic issues in the context of this pandemic is to be prepared and discussed in political lessons at school and outside school (F.Zeilner).

The State is called upon to act: A collision of interests (freedom and health)

It is very important here to show the pupils that the state is prompted by the Corona crisis to find a balance between the freedom of people or the individual and security (protective function). This also means a collision of interests. In political education this also leads to many questions, especially concerning long-term political, social and economic consequences. This also includes the problem-solving competence of liberal democracies, the topic of globalisation, the possibilities of the European Union (EU) to solve problems, etc. (F.Zeilner).

III. THE FRAMEWORK AND ANCHORING OF POLITICAL EDUCATION IN THE AUSTRIAN SCHOOL SYSTEM

1. THE DECREE OF PRINCIPLE AS A TEACHING PRINCIPLE

In the Austrian school system, civic education is anchored in various ways. Since 1978, it has been enshrined as a teaching principle primarily in the Basic Decree. This decree, which is updated in 2015, also defines the three pillars of civic education. These are:

- 1) Political education as an independent subject or as a combination of subjects.
- 2) Political education through school participation of pupils
- 3) Civic education as a cross-curricular teaching principle that is intended to develop democratic competences in all subjects (Basic Decree 2015).

The foundations, objectives and implementation of civic education in Austrian schools are laid down in this basic decree. In addition to national (Austrian) standards, this decree also refers to the Council of Europe Charter on Political Education and Human Rights Education. The teaching principle of civic education, which has existed since 1978, applies to all school types; the combination subjects in school forms of the first and second secondary levels currently have different names (Basic Law 2015).

2. THE BEUTELBACHER CONSENSUS OF 1976

Another important framework for civic education is the Beutelsbach Consensus of 1976, which defines the generally recognised minimum conditions (Minimalkonsens). Civic education here must be based on three basic principles. These are the prohibition of indoctrination, the imperative of controversy and balance, and the principle of addressee orientation (Beutelsbacher Konsens 1976).

Some developments in the context of political education have already led to criticism, in particular that principles of the Beutelsbach Consensus are being disregarded. This was also pointed out, for example, in Lösch's publication "International and European Conditions of Political Education - Criticising European Citizenship Education". Lösch is of the opinion that the understanding of identity as a learning goal of European citizenship education is also criticised by political didactics. The principles of the Beutelsbach Consensus are disregarded

here, such as the controversy principle and the prohibition of overwhelming (Lösch 2009, p. 856).

3. THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

Political education refers not only to the politics of the nation state but also to international politics. The international, European and global context is very important in the present. The international level of civic education or political education is already very diverse. The Council of Europe is also of great importance here, which, for example, uses the Framework of Reference for Democratic Competences to describe concrete competences that pupils and students need in the context of civic education (Council of Europe: Reference Framework for Democratic Competences).

European political education is also anchored in the curricula in Austria. Both "Education for Europe" and "Education about Europe" are essential here. In the context of "Education for Europe", pupils should above all be shown the process of a politically united or unifying Europe. They are to acquire competences in order to be able to participate actively in this process (Schmuck 1991b, p. 322).

IV. POLITICAL EDUCATION IN THE UNDERSTANDING OF THE PRESENT

1. THE FOCUS IS ON THE TRANSFER OF POLITICAL COMPETENCES

Political education or political education focuses on political problem areas (issues) of the present. These include, for example, democracy, human rights, peace or peace education, migration, media, equality between men and women, etc., and deal with these issues. In addition, historical contexts and opportunities for political participation, in particular opportunities to influence decisions, are also important in this context. This also applies to the topic of democratic schools, which is, however, controversially discussed (F.Zeilner).

Political education can be understood as the sum of "key competences", which, however, go beyond classical institutional theory. Civic education is not to be understood as civic education, citizenship education or institutional education, but in the field of contemporary

civic education, the focus is on conveying political competences. Here the Austrian competence structure model for civic education created the basis for enabling pupils and young people to actively participate in political events and to find their way around this subject (Krammer 2008).

The aim of competence-oriented teaching is a reflected and (self-)reflexive political awareness, which is built up in the context of school learning in a special way by means of exemplary approaches to political topics, taking into account the pupils' life and experience. The life and experience of pupils in the context of politics, political education and digital media is also the focus of research. At present, political education refers in particular to the manifold activities of the Federal Government, the countries, international and supranational organisations and also to those of non-governmental organisations (NGOs). Here, politically relevant competences, the ability to make political judgements and act and methodological skills for orientation within a complex political world are essential. The use of digital media, political interests, participation, political responsibility, normative questions of society etc. are central areas in the overall context. In addition, "school democracy" and its actors (democratic school) should make a substantial contribution to political education. This is also political education through school participation of pupils. Contemporary political education is no longer conceptually conceivable without a diversity of perspectives or multi-perspectivity. This applies to both school and non-school education, which should be considered as a whole (Sander 2005).

2. THE GLOBAL CONTEXT OF POLITICAL EDUCATION

2.1. Different terms for political education

There are very different terms for civic education, democracy education, democracy learning etc. For example, terms from the Anglo-American area cannot be directly adopted in the German language. However, clarifying terms, especially in a global context, is essential. One reason for this is that an increasing interest in civic education and a democratic-political orientation of civic education is being observed, particularly in European or nation-state democracies. The investigation of debates and trends on political education in individual countries in this context is very important here, as is the conceptual clarification and specification of political education and de-democracy education or democracy learning.

Especially in the context of European orientation and cooperation. The term "civic education" which is commonly used in the German-speaking world is less precise than, for example, the English term "Education for Democratic Citizenship". "Education for democratic citizenship" is now a common translation here (Diendorfer 2006, p 9 f).

2.2. Policy learning in a national and global context

Current globalisation and world social discourse, including reference theories, are also topical in the present, both for the field of science and for teaching politics. It can be assumed that worldwide developments also have an impact on the educational system and political education. There are already several research approaches on this topic. Above all, the current discussion of globalisation and world society is of major importance here. In order to explain global developments in the field of education, reference theories are of particular research interest. Three of these are very topical, which can be described with the terms "world society" (Luhmann), "world culture" (Meyer) and "world system" (Wallerstein) (Koch/Schemmann 2009).

In the field of education, however, the different access to education, including access to media, especially digital media, is relevant. The topic of the "digital divide" is very important in principle, but especially in education, especially in political education. It is associated with different educational opportunities for people, with many positive or negative consequences. This also includes questions such as "Which terms and expressions do political educators use in class, also in a global context? (Zeilner F.).

It should also be questioned here what these terms or these terms in connection with modern developments mean in concrete terms for political education in schools. It can be assumed that modern developments in the education system can also affect the everyday life of pupils. Global dimensions, global (living) spaces (especially virtual ones), global learning etc. are already part of their everyday life. Global Citizenship Education has become an important concept in the context of civic education. An investigation of global dimensions and the internationalisation of (political) education are essential for the education sector. Global Citizenship Education and Global Learning are particularly topical today, and their connection was already highlighted in the final declaration of Maastricht in 2002 (reference document: final declaration of the Maastricht Conference 2002).

2.3. Global learning and civic education: an inclusive learning concept

Global learning as an educational concept also requires civic education. Global learning is understood as an educational response to globalisation processes, which is why political content is very essential. It is attempted here to think and act with a view to the whole world, which is also very essential for educators and pupils. The topic "global learning and political education" requires competences and adaptive abilities of teachers and pupils and an optimal quality framework (democratic school) in which this current and complex topic can be dealt with. This also includes the interconnections of current global social, political, ecological and economic developments, the background of which must also be shown (F.Zeilner).

2.4. The issue of European political education

We live in Europe: education for pan-European thinking is essential

We live in Europe, so we should also feel "European". But this does not apply to all people living in Europe. In the field of education, the essential questions here include "How important is Europe for civic education, how important is civic education for Europe? Pan-European subject areas are already the content of political education in the Austrian school sector. The topic of Europe in the field of education covers much more than the European Union (EU), not only geographically but also politically, socially and economically. For example, 47 countries are currently also members of the Council of Europe, the oldest confederation of states on the European continent (Centre polis-Politik Lernen in der Schule).

In the Austrian school sector, the topic or educational goal of Europe is anchored in lessons, inter alia, via the teaching principle of political education, which also includes European political education. In teaching practice, this means that every educator in every school type, every school level and in every university has to be aware of the fact that the topic or the educational goal of Europe is not only a topic but also an objective.

The aim is to integrate the theme of Europe or European themes into the classroom in the subject. Based on the decree of principle for the teaching principle "political education",

which was re-issued in 2015, "education for pan-European thinking" is mentioned as one of the main concerns of political education or European political education (www.bmb.gv.at/europabildung)

The topic of Europe is also present in the Austrian curricula, both in primary school, NMS or MS, AHS and BMHS. The polis centre provides support for teachers, as it does for political education in general. The dossier covers essential topics such as education, democracy, peace, digitalisation, media competence, human rights, etc. In addition to Europeanisation, globalisation and internationalisation have made new forms of political participation necessary, especially the use of digital media, such as the Internet (Zentrum polis-Politik Lernen in der Schule).

The internationalisation of education:

The issue of internationalisation of education or of schools, including colleges, teacher training colleges and universities, is particularly topical at present. This includes international educational cooperation. This also means an exchange of knowledge across national borders. Until the 20th century, this was basically an initiative of individual persons or institutions. In the present day, the internationalisation of schools is also being promoted through support programmes. This also includes support programmes for political education, democratic education, etc. Internationalisation of education in the field of democratic-political education is also taking place as a result of international developments. The internationalisation and Europeanisation of political and economic processes also has an impact on the conditions for democracy education. Before these developments, a nation-state orientation was the rule in terms of content and institutions. However, the possible effects of these developments on education for democratic politics are controversially discussed. Important questions here include "Whether and to what extent will this open up new content and opportunities?". "Will the established practice be narrowed or widened?" The main topics of discussion are the understanding of democracy and the perspectives of "European Citizenship Education" and expanded "Global Citizenship Education". This also includes a world perspective that transcends a Europe-centred view and implies internationalisation or globalisation (Lösch 2009, p. 849).

The issue of Europe must be viewed critically:

The topic of Europe should be prepared and taught in an interesting way for pupils, but it must also be viewed critically. The integration of new countries and policy areas has so far led to a stable peace order and growing prosperity. This is of considerable importance in the present and the future. The banishment of wars from the European continent, many crises, lack of democracy, freedom of movement or its restriction, e.g. by the Covid-19 situation, etc., require education, European political education, especially democratic political education. The European Union was and is also intended to secure peace, which is to be demonstrated above all in the field of education. Negative developments in nation states, in Europe and also worldwide make this particularly necessary. European political education and education for democracy are a necessary condition here. Nationalism is already on the rise again in some nation states, but this is contrary to the idea of a united Europe (F. Zeilner).

2.5. The issue of development education

Development education work in the Austrian school system is based on the "Grundsatzrlass Politische Bildung" (Decree on Political Education). This decree of 1978, which was last reissued in 2015, defines "education for openness to the world, based on an understanding of the existential problems of humanity" as one of the important concerns of political education (decree on political education).

Development education work is challenged by worldwide current topics such as education, democracy, peace, globalisation, climate crisis, human rights, migration, ecology, economy etc. Development education, especially the topics "economy and ecology", are very important for the political education of today. Development education aims to convey the model of a worldwide sustainable development. This model stands for economic performance, social justice, ecological sustainability and good governance. It is also intended to show the interrelationships of current global social, political, ecological and economic developments. In the field of education, it is of interest to address "local" and "global" (life) facts and to show how these are connected. The topics of economy and ecology (e.g. consumer behaviour, environmental protection, globalisation etc.) are fundamentally essential for political education, but above all in the context of the everyday

life of pupils and their associated political interests. An optimal quality framework (democratic school, its actors, information technologies, etc.) for global learning and civic education, including the use of digital media, is certainly necessary here. In contemporary political education, the use of digital media is an absolute necessity both in political education related to the nation state and above all in the context of European, international and global developments and educational content (decree of principle 2015).

V. EUROPEAN, INTERNATIONAL AND GLOBAL DEVELOPMENTS (SELECTION)

1. EDUCATION FOR DEMOCRATIC CITIZENSHIP (EDC)

1.1. The Council of Europe's democratic education project in 1997

The Council of Europe's democracy education project began in 1997 and ended in 2009, when the ideas of "Human Rights Education" (HRE) and the "Education for Democratic Citizenship" (EDC) initiated by UNESCO were recognised and taken up as very essential. With this project, the Council of Europe took up already existing impulses and developed an education policy programme and reform project for its member states. This idea of citizenship education, initiated on a global level, became a comprehensive concept of educational reform and the development of a democratic political culture (Lange/Volker 2007, p. 157).

Even then, the generic term "Education for Democratic Citizenship (EDC)" was established. However, there is no direct translation of this term into the German language. In Austria, especially in the context of the school system, the term political education is mainly used. In Germany, democratic education was chosen. At the time, political education was considered by the German decision-makers for the "European Year of Democracy Education" to be misleading and "too much part of the German debate" <http://www.bpb.de/apuz/148214/politische-bildung--in-europa>, p. 1; cf. also Dürr et al., p. 6).

The addition "democratic" clearly distinguishes "Education for Democratic Citizenship" from the language used in the European Union. This addition shows in particular the high value of democracy and the political relevance of education. Two years later, the focus was

already on the connection with human rights education, which was and is "Human Rights Education" <http://www.bpb.de/apuz/148214/politische-bildung--in-europa>, p. 1 f).

In this context, the justification for the European Year was also essential, stating that "EDC includes in particular human rights education, civic education, peace education and intercultural learning. The concepts of democratisation and participation are closely linked to this (Council of Europe, leaflet on the European Year "Education for Democratic Citizenship", 2007).

2. GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION (GCED)

Global Citizenship Education (GCED) in order to help build peaceful and sustainable societies (Jöran and others, Agency for Education). Global Citizenship Education is a concept that combines different approaches to improve the world through education. GCED is a form of civic learning in which students also actively participate in projects that address global, social, political, economic or environmental issues (UNESCO 2014, Global Citizenship Education. Preparing Learners for the Challenges of the 21st Century, UNESCO Paris).

Global Citizenship Education can be understood as a comprehensive combination of political education, global learning, intercultural education and peace education. Democratic values and the development of a global, peaceful and pluralistic society are very important here (<http://www.globaleslernen.at/home.html>, p. 1).

The internationalisation and globalisation of civic education must be promoted. The educational approach Global Citizenship Education, focuses on (political) education for the world society with the aim of promoting the development and promotion of competences for a responsible participation in world social developments. Key issues of the present are central contents here (<https://www.uni-klu.ac.at/frieden/inhalt>, p 1).

3. EUROPEAN CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION

European Citizenship Education is a central theme in modern political education. However, it is fundamentally difficult to define political education in a European context and according to European standards. The topic of Europe in the context of educational offers is an

essential part of the curriculum, especially in the member states of the European Union. For example, in the political education in and outside schools in Austria and other countries. A critical appraisal of the state of knowledge is certainly essential here (Becker 2011, p 33 ff). European political education, which is essential in the school sector, has a multifaceted appearance and is very important in the Austrian school system. Euro-political education is an important component of political education and essential for political learning processes. The background of political learning processes, political participation, political education, European political education, etc. shows a multifaceted appearance with important tasks and reveals decisive challenges for the present and the future, which are also in clear political and socio-political contexts (Zeilner 2014).

European Citizenship Education means a Europeanisation of civic education, where the achievement of expertise and judgement by students is a key objective. Following the initiative of UNE-SCO and the Council of Europe, the EDC major project aims in particular at a Europeanisation of political education in the sense of an exchange of information and increased cooperation between institutions and political educators within the member states. To this end, educational policy and pedagogical-didactic programmes have been developed and networked throughout Europe, which aim to promote political education and learning about democracy both through democratic-pedagogical suggestions for school and curriculum development and through subject-related didactic approaches to social and political learning in the classroom.

To this end, educational policy and pedagogical-didactic programmes have been developed and networked throughout Europe, which seek to promote political education and learning about democracy both through democratic-pedagogical suggestions for school and curriculum development and through subject-related didactic approaches to social and political learning in the classroom. Accompanying studies documented on the one hand the initial state of political education and democratic school and learning culture in the European member states and on the other hand the success and possible barriers to implementation of the EDC programmes. Last but not least, European Citizenship Education aims at the question of how to impart Europe-related competences to promote European (Union) citizenship and identity. In any case, this requires global learning in the context of the global knowledge society (Lange/Volker 2007, p. 156, cf. also Breit 2005, p. 108 ff).

VI. DIGITAL MEDIA IN THE CONTEXT OF (POLITICAL) EDUCATION AND EVERYDAY LIFE

1. THE BEGINNING

Predecessors of the computer have been around since ancient times, and modern computer technology developed very quickly in comparison with other electrical devices of modern times. In particular, the entire 20th century was essential for developments in the context of the computer. By the early 1980s, the technology had matured to such an extent that companies, educational institutions and private users were able to benefit from the use of computers. From around the mid-1980s onwards, computers were also common in (higher) schools in Austria. Rapid developments then led to numerous business start-ups in the context of information technology. Examples are Apple, IBM and Microsoft. Rapid developments in computers and the entire information technology sector are clearly present in the 21st century (www.geschichte.oesterreich.com, S 1 ff).

2. NEW TERMS

This is also where (new) terms have emerged, such as industry 4.0, business 4.0 and education 4.0. The basis for education 4.0 is access to broadband internet. Broadband Internet access (broadband access) is access to the Internet with a relatively high data transmission rate. Pupils and students must have a wide range of digital tools at their disposal, including digital pedagogy. From today's point of view, the future of people is very digital. Pupils and students have to be prepared for a digital professional and private future in the context of education systems. Advantages and disadvantages of digitisation have to be clearly shown here, especially in the context of the topic of health. Exercise and sport, movement in the great outdoors, etc. without information technology (in risk areas but with mobile phones and safety equipment, etc.) is very important. Furthermore, an "earth" should not be forgotten. Experiencing nature, living in and with nature is very suitable here (F.Zeilner).

3. MEDIA DEMOCRACY AND INFORMATION IN DIGITAL MEDIA

3.1. The mediatisation of policy or policy areas

Towards the end of the 20th century, the term "media democracy" was already established alongside terms used in the context of computer technology. This term is mainly used to emphasize the great importance of mass media – including digital media. Here (digital) media are themselves politically effective actors who also have a decisive influence on the formation of opinion and thus on the scope for political action. Actors in the media sector and politics are generally closely connected. Political areas are increasingly mediatised, and both fields of action overlap. Politics often subjects itself to the so-called "media logic", where information, both analogue and digital, is very important. (Mediendemokratie- Demokratie- Zentrum Wien, p 1 ff).

3.2. Shift to the mass media level

Standard functions of the mass media include communicative tasks which are attributed to the media in a democratic society. They also include those services which media basically provide for people. The media are therefore also involved in the functioning of a social system and its development possibilities (Burkart 2002, p 378 f).

According to Ronneberger, the media have to fulfil various political functions or are brought into such contexts. In the context of politics and political education, they are not only political mediators (knowledge mediators) but much more. In this context, the creation of publicity is also very important, especially in the field of media democracy, which can already be spoken of in Austria towards the end of the 20th century (Filzmeier 2006, p 39; Ronneberger 1974, p 197 ff).

Accordingly, since about the year 2000, political education in the schools of Austria and politics have fundamentally changed in such a way that a so-called "media democracy" was already predominant, analogous to comparable communication societies. The teaching of the curriculum and the teaching of politics increasingly withdrew from interpersonal contacts and shifted to the mass media level (Filzmeier 2006, p. 39).

3.3. Media interest in political issues

As a result, political issues that are of interest to the mass media or are dealt with in a media democracy have become or are now of general and specific interest. Citizens receive information on current political issues mainly from the media. Representatives of the media provide information themselves, they also prepare it and comment on it themselves. In this way, they act as a guiding force. The media have long since ceased to play only the role of a policy-mediating observer and controller; they are also policy-makers for specific issues. Mass media influence political events to a considerable extent. In many cases, they also shape politically effective public opinion. The effect of great publicity is particularly significant here (Hillgruber, in: Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung, 12. Februar 2003).

4. THE BEGINNING OF THE DIGITAL AGE

In the scientific field, it is assumed that 2002 was the year in which mankind was already able to store more information in digital than in analogue media. That was the beginning of the digital age with rapid developments of digital media, which are however very dynamic. Regarding the use of digital media in (political) education, the statement "Digital media are not good or bad per se" is essential, it is the people who use them. This applies here above all to the selection and preparation of teaching and learning content and the existence of necessary skills. This can lead to more efficient teaching and increased motivation to learn, both in principle and in political education. The use of digital media should be seen as an extended possibility for teaching and learning. Above all, media competence is necessary for pupils to cope well in the digital world. An active, self-determined life in as much freedom as possible is very important for people of the present and the future, and education is absolutely necessary for this. Among other subjects, political education is very suitable to thematise this, but above all also to acquire and apply digital competences in different areas of competence. Especially in the context of globalisation. But (possible) negative influences of computer technology must always be kept in mind (F. Zeilner).

5. DIGITAL COMPETENCE AREAS

5.1. Digital basic education at all school levels: digi.komp

For many years now, digital competences and informatics education have been enshrined in Austrian curricula, teaching principles and educational concerns.

The common digi.komp umbrella is also essential for the implementation of the binding guidelines from primary school to secondary level 2. It is shown here which skills are specifically meant by the "autonomous, reflective use of information and communication technologies" mentioned in the curriculum. It enables teachers to use digital and IT skills in a planned and integrative way in subject lessons (politics lessons). The competence model digi.komp encompasses the partial aspects of information technology, people and society, IT systems, applications and concepts (www.bmbwf.gv.at/zrp/dibi/dgb, p. 1).

5.2. Recommendation to EU governments

In 2006, the European Parliament and the Council issued a recommendation calling on EU governments to implement the European reference framework for lifelong learning. This reference framework includes "digital literacy" as one of eight key competences. In 2009, the European Commission also recommended that the EU Member States promote media literacy in the digital world (www.rechnungshof.gv.at, p 127).

Figure: Digital competence areas (source: www.rechnungshof.gv.at, p. 127).

6. (DIGITAL) MEDIA AND POLITICAL COMMUNICATION

(Digital) Media and political communication is also an issue in the context of teaching politics in schools. It opens up many questions, especially through European, international and global developments and contexts. The media are also referred to as the fourth power in the state, which in any case also includes political information, political communication and political participation. Current questions here are, for example, "How can political media or political information conveyed by the media be analysed? How can such content be prepared in a way that is interesting for pupils? How do pupils use digital (social) media in everyday life and for political education at school?" Media competence of pupils and teachers is an essential prerequisite here, political education has to be taught to pupils in a process-oriented way and should basically also include topics concerning their everyday life. This also promotes the interest in politics (F.Zeilner).

The already very large spectrum of political forms of participation is particularly important for pupils and students, it must be shown to them and well prepared. The intensity here ranges, for example, from opportunities for co-determination, participation and co-determination to jointly responsible self-determination. These are often very complex subject areas which also affect the controversially discussed topic of democracy in schools (polis aktuell No.4 2012, p 6).

Complex subject areas or facts should be presented in a simplified, understandable and interactive way in the classroom. The aim of using media, especially digital media in class, is to simplify complex subjects and to present them in a more understandable and interactive way. Pupils can also work on a topic themselves, practise it, present it or give a lecture on it, etc. Apps are also important in the present day because they offer the possibility to practice and consolidate a certain subject in a playful way. For political content, especially political communication, democracy learning, etc., there are numerous learning opportunities on the Internet. Political simulation games are very topical here. A correct selection and a good preparation for teaching are necessary (F.Zeilner).

7. DIGITAL MEDIA ARE VERY DYNAMIC

Politics affects our everyday life, which is why political interest – which basically correlates with specific political topics – and competences, especially political and digital competences,

of pupils and pedagogues are necessary. Political education should promote both, especially the correct use of (digital) media. It can be assumed that digital media (social media) are very dynamic and must therefore be constantly redefined and examined in a target group-specific way (e.g. pupils in upper secondary schools). Students can create personal narratives and interpretations of political content on social media platforms such as Twitter, Tumblr, Facebook, etc. and have them commented on in the communities. In contrast to conventional discussion forums and chatrooms, social media channels have a much larger user base. This is further enhanced by diversity and the dynamics of digital change (<https://science.apa.at>, p 1 f).

8. THE CORE COMPETENCIES

Core competences are required for the use of digital media in teaching in general, and especially for the recognition of (possible) potential. These are in particular media competence and media pedagogical competence. A keynote speech on the subject of core competences by Thomas Krüger, President of the Federal Agency for Civic Education in Germany, is also of interest. Here he expressed the view that the new media have already changed the political decision-making process in the entire population. In particular, the Internet has replaced many other media as a source of research and information. Political education had to focus on five core competences due to the many changes in the media sector and digitalisation. These are:

- 1) Civic education must rethink the promotion of skills and in particular develop media competence in globalised societies.
- 2) Civic education must strengthen social competence and trust by acting as a lobbyist for more citizen participation.
- 3) Civic education must provide a platform for discourse and debate, with a particular emphasis on interaction, as is the case with Wahl-O-Mat.
- 4) Civic education has to speak out on the net and in social networks.
- 5) Civic education must have the courage to lose control, to reflect more strongly and to activate the participants (Krüger Thomas).

Krüger's keynote speech was followed by a discussion in which the opportunities of the Internet as a method and tool in learning situations were also pointed out. In this context, teaching must become more dialogue-based and even more project-oriented.

In particular, the increasing heterogeneity of the target groups requires individual learning scenarios, new learning partnerships to reach these target groups and, above all, an intelligent combination of low-threshold introductory offers with sustainable educational offers (www.kas.de).

In this context, the Internet as an online medium opens up an educational offer and a potential for participation, because users, unlike newspapers or television, do not have to remain in their role as recipients of the information offered, but can themselves help to shape the media offer and use the Internet and its services as a platform for political content and political activities. This is essential for the education sector and also motivating in principle (<https://m.bpb.de/lexika/internet>, p 1 ff).

9. THE INTERNET AS PART OF EVERYDAY LIFE

For many pupils, the Internet, especially applications and services of the Social Web, such as blogs and social networking sites, are already part of their everyday life; they are also used for political participation. The Internet has significantly changed many areas of life, including political education. These changes in detail were and are also in the interest of research. The "Allensbach Study", for example, which clearly shows how the Internet is changing politics (<https://www.welt.de/deutschland>, Allensbach Study), has already produced very interesting results.

In order to be able to assess this, education, especially political education, is important. It is an essential goal to educate responsible citizens who are able to act in existing political, economic and social systems and who are also able to analyse structures of power and rule, to form a critically reflected judgement, to learn and master strategies of action in order to not only have a say but also to actively influence political processes. The use of digital media is certainly necessary here. With their potential, they can also make a fundamental contribution to the "democratisation of education". The educational opportunities that have arisen or are emerging here are also an expression of a changed understanding of learning and education, they are changing not only learning in the school sector but also in other areas of education (Kenner/Lange 2017, p 1 ff). User behaviour, especially in everyday life, is

becoming increasingly intensive. Here, however, it should also be noted that being "online" for a long time can lead to difficulties in real life. For example, in distinguishing the "real" from the "virtual" world. In principle, this also includes potential dangers. Negative changes in the behaviour of pupils or children, also among adults, must be recognised in time, because countermeasures are necessary. Face-to-face" communication remains indispensable alongside the use of digital media. Physical social contacts are absolutely necessary in people's lives (Po-litische Bildung und Neue Medien. Bericht der Transferstelle politische Bildung zum Jah-resthema 2015, S 5).

It can be assumed that political educators are not or not sufficiently aware of how students use digital media – especially in the form of social media – in the context of politics and political education. Students can also produce and publish political (historical etc.) content for a large audience, e.g. on YouTube etc. This also opens up an interesting field of research (F.Zeilner).

VII. DIGITAL MEDIA IN POLITICAL EDUCATION: NETWORK POLICY EDUCATION OR DIGITAL EDUCATION

1. THE USE OF DIGITAL MEDIA IN TEACHING POLITICS

Network policy education or digital education is a current and very important topic in the present. This means above all the use of digital media in (political) education and requires in particular a considered and critical approach to Internet sources, social media etc. Digital media are not good or bad per se, it depends on the people who use them, and this has already been described. "Digital natives" are in great demand in the context of "net-political education", it requires or includes more learning support than knowledge transfer. This also means learning with digital media and learning via digital media. Apart from sound theoretical competences, "learning by doing" is very important here. In the context of media democracy and modern political education, net-political education or digital education is an absolute necessity (F.Zeilner).

2. MEDIA COMPETENCE FOR TEACHERS AND PUPILS

In any case, this development also requires media competence on the part of teachers, students and pupils, above all a professionalisation of media competence promotion in the context of (democratic) political education (Hugger 2017, p 182 f).

This includes the need for digital basic education – which is already available in the Austrian school system – in the context of "network policy education". Net political education is also political communication in the context of digital media with interesting and essential areas, such as democracy as a cooperation project, etc. Technical developments such as Web 2.0 and its various technologies are present in many areas of life. This also includes the areas of politics and political education, where it is basically possible to obtain political content and results quickly and efficiently. This enables both passive and active political participation (<https://lpb.sachsen-anhalt.de>> politische Kommunikation im Kontext neuer Medien, S 1 f). In the context of the culture of active participation, such as the creation of one's own videos, posting texts, setting up platforms, etc. and the communicative exchange with persons and groups of persons, the attitude of expectation towards political actors and other social institutions also improves in principle. Here, the thought pattern of networking and sharing (political) digital contents with each other is transferred to other areas of life. (Information) platforms are very topical here, for example (Maier-Rabler et al, p 19).

Information platforms on civic education already offer many subject areas in a national and global context. Pupils can also use social media platforms such as Twitter, Tumblr and Facebook to offer personal narratives and interpretations and have them commented on in the communities. Against this background and the increasing complexity of political (including economic and social) interrelationships, growing internationalisation and globalisation, it must also be assumed that a solid digital basic education for pupils (and teachers) is particularly important (digi.komp: Digitale Grundbildung in allen Schulstufen; BGBl.II Nr.71/2018).

3. A DIGITAL BASIC EDUCATION FOR PUPILS

3.1. Prescribed curriculum for the compulsory exercise "Digital literacy"

Above all, in order to be able to cope well with the opportunities for political participation via the Internet in the context of the education system, globalisation etc., "digital basic

education" is an essential prerequisite. For this reason, as already shown, a prescribed curriculum for the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education" at (new) secondary schools and AHS lower grades was introduced in the Austrian school system from the 2018/2019 school year ([https:// lehrerweb. wien> single>news](https://lehrerweb.wien>single>news), Schule 4.0: Neue Medien und Lerntechnologien in Theorie und Praxis, p 1 ff).

This digital basic education with the aim of teaching pupils an informed, safe, responsible and reflective use of media and modern technology is divided into areas of competence. These are digital competence, media competence and political competence. The acquisition of digital competences refers to the selection and application of suitable tools and methods. The basis for enabling the acquisition and development of digital competences is the teaching of hardware and software skills. The acquisition and extension of "media competence" is to be understood and reflected on media use, media language and media content. Critical and creative thinking is very important here. Political competences are of great importance for political education, which also enables a better understanding of democracy, freedom of expression etc. ([https://lehrerweb. wien> single>news](https://lehrerweb.wien>single>news), Schule 4.0: Neue Medien und Lerntechnologien in Theorie und Praxis, S 1 ff).

Modern political education must be present online in order to make the most of its potential. With reference to the "Beutelsbach Consensus", political education must be represented where political processes take place. It is not an actor in these processes – in the sense of the prohibition of overwhelming and controversy – but it must be accessible to those who ask questions, even where these people are. The Internet with "open access" is very important here (<https://lpb.sachsen-anhalt.de>politische Kommunikation im Kontext neuer Medien>, S 1f).

3.2. Learning with and through digital media

In the educational sector and the school system, both "learning with digital media" and "learning via digital media" are of relevance to digitisation. This is essential for didactic and methodological considerations, especially for media competence. Here, digital media are not only tools but also "digital actors". This must be clearly demonstrated in the context of political education ([http:// www.bpb.de/ lernen/digitale-bildung/ medienpädagogik/ 257449/ digitale-welt-al..., S 1](http://www.bpb.de/ lernen/digitale-bildung/ medienpädagogik/ 257449/ digitale-welt-al..., S 1)).

Digitisation also requires new approaches to learning, which are absolutely necessary alongside good teachers. Learning with and for digitisation means above all explaining independently acquired knowledge, discussing and practising it in a team, and also implementing it and paying attention to results. This is a completely new "mindset" and requires an overall plan for implementation in the education system, which covers all aspects of education. Traditional teaching can be improved and supplemented by digital media. In education, too, digitisation and the use of digital media opens up new opportunities for learners and teachers (Hellmuth 2016, p. 1 ff).

In the opinion of important female teachers, however, textbooks will not disappear as a result. The use of digital media is particularly suitable for compact or short information, and a differentiated view of content must be taken very seriously here. Media competence is very important in this context and must be acquired and developed further. In history and politics lessons, an analytic, critical view of political developments is necessary (Hellmuth 2016, p 1 ff). Media literacy is essential during school life and beyond, i.e. for the rest of life. Media play a fundamental role in political participation both in and outside school. This continues after school life, where the media can continue to play an important role in political participation. For this reason, the targeted use of (mass) media and the achievement of media competence in political education is of great importance (Klafki 1991, p 49 ff).

3.3. Possible potentials of digital media

An individually supportive teaching and learning culture is essential:

Digital media basically have great potential for teaching, as can be proven by research results and publications. An essential prerequisite here is that their use is embedded in an individually supportive teaching and learning culture. Contents, paths and learning methods can be adapted to individual pupils, thus enabling pupils to learn successfully according to their individual prerequisites and supported by the use of digital media in teaching. Digital media are "tools" which, if used correctly, enable action- and development-oriented teaching (<https://www.netzwerk-digitale-bildung.de>>, S 1 ff).

Teaching and learning must each start from a task that is important for pupils. In the context of political education these are, for example, problem tasks, decision-making tasks, design tasks, assessment tasks, etc. The correct selection and preparation of political topics, the

relevant tasks and the use of digital media can certainly achieve good learning outcomes which also show existing potential. Digital media or digital technologies are part of the everyday life of many people, they are particularly relevant for young people. However, the individual situation is essential here and must be ascertained by teachers (<https://www.netzwerk-digitale-bildung.de>), p 1 ff). (Political) education basically starts at home and is continued at school. Here the different school forms are very important for the provision of civic education. Studies in Germany and other countries show that the most favourable situation is in high schools, while the least favourable situation is in vocational schools, etc. This also correlates with media competence and, in principle, with the possible applications of digital media. (Anchour Sabine).

4. EXAMPLES OF CURRENT STUDIES: RESEARCH RESULTS FROM THE HUMBOLT UNIVERSITY OF BERLIN, LANCASTER UNIVERSITY AND THE UNIVERSITY OF VIENNA:

Study: Digital media are not good or bad per se (Research by Humbolt University of Berlin)

In the area of classroom research, Heike Schaumburg's research findings on the potential and risks of digital media in the classroom are particularly important. According to Schaumburg, research on digital media indicates that the pedagogues are very decisive. It is not the media themselves that are important, but how they are integrated into teaching (Heike Schaumburg, Humbolt University of Berlin, 2019).

Study: Advantages of teaching with digital media from the point of view of pedagogues and pupils (Study report by Lancaster University)

A research result on the influence of digital media on the learning process was achieved through a joint research project between the University of Lancaster and high school in Solingen. At this school, researchers from Lancaster University provided scientific support for the introduction and use of two SMART Boards for eight months (study report from Lancaster University).

The main research result was that the use of digital media improved the learning process in the subjects studied. The Lancaster study claims that the interactive boards were initially only made available in a few rooms for selected subjects, because this way the new

technology could be tried out in peace and quiet. A regular exchange of experience between teachers and pupils is important and can also increase the acceptance of the technology. This study also shows the advantages in the classroom. Above all, to use learning content that focuses on participation, clarity, understanding and efficiency. At home, content that is based on recreation, reflection and review is important (Lancaster University study report).

In addition to the advantages of didactic use of the potentials of digital media, teachers and pupils also mentioned essential advantages of teaching with digital media. These are:

- Greater interest and participation. The oral participation of the students in class was significantly better.
- A faster and more interactive way of working. Contents of individual lessons could be worked through faster. This meant that the learners were attentive and concentrated for longer.
- A more intensive exchange and better understanding. Pupils discussed more often, learned from each other and thus understood the topics dealt with better.
- A spatially and temporally flexible access to teaching content. Learners could repeat the material they had learned at school at home and access online resources in the virtual learning environment.
- Higher visibility and audio quality. Lesson content was more clearly recognised throughout the classroom and audio content was very well understood.
- Efficient teaching with a wide range of possibilities. The pedagogues could switch between different materials and media on the digital whiteboard (Lancaster University study report).

Study: "Learning under COVID-19" (University of Vienna)

Since about mid-March 2020, the closure of the universities and the suspension of teaching at schools in Austria have changed the everyday life of pupils and students considerably. With this study, a research team of the Faculty of Psychology at the University of Vienna wanted to find out how pupils and students cope with the current situation and distance learning. The main aim of the study was to identify the challenges and possible new learning paths. Pupils and students were interviewed at three different points in time.

What were or are the objectives of the study?

A research team from the Faculty of Psychology at the University of Vienna wanted to find out more about how students are coping with the current situation and home learning, what challenges are involved and whether the changed situation is opening up new learning pathways. A series of surveys was conducted. For the present first analyses of this study, the answers of a first sub-sample (sample: 8349 pupils) between ten (10) and nineteen (19) years of age were used in an online questionnaire (cut-off date 20.4.2020). Of these, 63% were female, 36% male and 1% other. 22% of those questioned stated that they (also) spoke languages other than German at home. Participation in the survey was voluntary, pupils with limited Internet access could not participate. The study is therefore not representative. It is assumed that risk groups tend to be underestimated.

First results of surveys with pupils: What has changed during the period of home learning?

- How to deal with the new learning situation?

The pupils interviewed stated that they spend an average of five (5) hours a day on school-related activities. Half of them spend between 3.5 and 6 hours on them, a quarter 3.5 hours or less. About 1% said that they only spend up to one hour a day on school-related activities. 16% of respondents said that they did not have a computer, laptop or tablet available for schoolwork. 21% do not receive any learning support within the family when they need it. 55% of the pupils receiving family support said that they receive it mainly from their mother. 70% make a plan for learning about tasks to be done, fixed daily learning times are followed by about 38% of respondents.

- What works well and what works not so well?

Most pupils find it particularly difficult to independently deal with the tasks. It is challenging not to receive oral instructions and to be able to ask questions only to a limited extent. It is also difficult to structure learning independently. Many pupils see improvements in their self-organisation. Computer skills are also being expanded and improved. These are also key competences that are also relevant for lifelong learning.

- What support do pupils need when learning from home? Overall, pupils feel well supported by their teachers. Only 3% do not know how to reach teachers in case of problems. Very

often, students wish for quicker feedback on tasks. Pupils see an important need for assistance in structuring their everyday learning and support in using information technology or computers. All e-learning units should take place uniformly on the same platform in order to maintain a better overview.

- What about their well-being?

About two thirds of the pupils feel comfortable despite the situation caused by Covid-19.

- Under what circumstances is the situation handled particularly well?

Getting along with e-learning is essential for successfully mastering the tasks in home learning. Pupils who do so well also receive clear instructions from teachers and are in regular contact with them. It is also important to know whether the tasks can be completed with the pupils' end devices.

- What are risk factors?

About 7% of the pupils interviewed indicated major problems in coping with the school requirements in the field of home learning. These pupils also have a low level of well-being and confidence. They also feel less connected to important people and have less contact with friends. Moreover, learning in particular cannot be organised well independently (Studie: „Lernen unter COVID-19“, Universität Wien. Erstergebnisse Befragung 1)

VIII. SUMMARY/REMARKS

According to the current state of research, the first written references to political education, or more precisely political education, can be found in ancient Greece from around 500 BC onwards.

Political education has been practised in Austria since the monarchy. Under the designation "civics" then "civic education", the main subjects taught were institutional studies and institutional teaching. This was basically knowledge of the constitution, government, parliament, judiciary etc. This teaching was associated with a rather conflict-averse understanding of politics, oriented towards maintaining the existing. The subject civics and civic education – law was taught for a very long time in the Austrian school system and was

replaced by (traditional) political education. This was an essential step. The importance of political education in the context of the education systems was already demonstrated by Adolf Exner in his inauguration speech at the University of Vienna in the 19th century. However, there was still a long way to go, with positive and negative developments, before the basic decree on the teaching principle of political education was issued in 1978, which laid down the foundations, objectives and implementation of political education in Austrian schools. In addition to national (Austrian) standards, this decree also refers, among other things, to the Council of Europe Charter on Political Education and Human Rights Education. Since the 21st century at the latest, multi-perspectivity and controversy have been didactic basic principles of political education. The focus is on the teaching of political competences. The Austrian competence structure model for political education created the basis for enabling pupils and young people to actively participate in political events and to find their way around this subject matter. At present, political education refers to the national state, to European, international and global contents. Here, politically relevant competences, the ability to make political judgements and act and methodological skills for orientation within a complex political world are essential. Political interest, participation, political responsibility, normative questions of society etc. are essential areas.

The political education changed from the ideal of the ruler to the educational effect on the ruling class, then to the importance of national education and finally to the own opinion and opinion-forming of the masses of the population. Mass media, especially digital media, are of great importance here.

The historical development of political education in the Austrian school system can be simplified to the steps of development from civics, civic education, political education, democratic education. At present, "Democratic Citizenship Education", "Global Citizenship Education", "European Citizenship Education" etc. are basically essential areas for political education. Media competence of pupils and teachers has also become increasingly important as a result. Media competence became necessary in 2001 at the latest when the discipline of "political education" became a compulsory subject of "history and political education" in the AHS. This was also an essential step for the sustainable development of the subject in the Austrian school sector.

Already towards the end of the 20th century, links between political education and other subjects became increasingly evident in Austria. At that time, the term media democracy was already topical, also with effects on political education. Only political topics that are of interest to the mass media or are dealt with there are of general interest in a "media

democracy". Dealing with media, especially digital media, became increasingly important. This means above all media competence, but it also requires substantially different competences of pupils and teachers.

Digital media have fundamentally brought about massive changes in political communication. With the pilot project 2017/2018 and the curriculum for the compulsory exercise "Digital Basic Education" 2018/2019, an important step towards mastering the use of digital media in teaching has already been taken in the Austrian school sector. This requires adaptations for all actors and means learning with digital media and learning via digital media. In this context the possibilities of political communication and political participation via the Internet are very diverse and also essential. Media can also be designed and distributed here. By electronic publishing and networking, a very large public can be reached. Above all, teachers and pupils can participate passively and actively in political communication and can also have their own content created and commented on. Digital media are not good or bad per se, they basically have great potential if the content is selected and prepared properly, e.g. political simulation games, apps, etc. This can also be the case in complex school and extracurricular contexts. As a result of scientific study results, it is not the media themselves that are important, but how they are integrated into teaching.

From my own teaching activities at vocational secondary and higher schools (BMHS), here also in the subject history and political education, and at a university, I also try to point out essential principles for the use of digital media in (political) education. For example, an online community has to be built up, but this is basically a long-term project and also requires good coordination of all actors. Central (political) contents or teaching and learning contents should be formulated briefly, clearly and easily understandable. Attention is also to be paid to videos and visual language, thus increasing awareness of concrete (political) issues. This also improves politisation in the social media. Information is processed cognitively better if it is supplemented with pictures or videos.

Political education is still integrated in other subjects. The demand for a separate teaching subject "political education" as a compulsory subject at Austrian schools has been raised for a long time by basically all political parties and representatives from the education sector. Its implementation would be an urgent necessity and requires above all an improvement of the framework conditions and the willingness to cooperate of all actors. Also more rationality in the school discussion, especially in the context of digitalisation and globalisation.

The current "corona pandemic" or "Covid-19" situation also has a major impact on education systems, as well as on the world of work. Above all, it accelerates changes and leads to distance learning and the "home office". Digital media and a lot of knowledge are a necessary condition for this. In the context of good political education, complex issues can be identified and dealt with. For some, solutions can also be considered and discussed. The present research work should also be seen as a plea for the introduction of a separate subject Political Education.

Franz Zeilner

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